

**IMPROVING SAFE WORK PERFORMANCE OF EMPLOYEES,
INCREASING WORK EFFICIENCY**

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ANNOTATION. The article discusses the growing importance of enhancing the safety and efficiency of workers in the development of industrial production networks, driven by the increasing demands for construction, production, and industry in Uzbekistan each year. The focus is on improving the health of workers and ensuring stable work performance in construction and industrial enterprises. Various measures aimed at creating a safe working environment and improving employee safety have been developed

KEY WORDS AND PHRASES: Creating a safe working environment, organizing labor protection, providing instructions, managing working hours and rest, conducting proper job analysis, ensuring safety, and fostering healthy work productivity

INTRODUCTION. The ultimate goal of all reforms in the economic and political spheres implemented in our country is to create decent living conditions for all citizens. Currently, the creation of such conditions in any society relies on scientific and technical progress. However, alongside the benefits of easing human labor, it introduces various dangerous factors leading to accidents like injuries and occupational diseases. Despite these challenges, everyone in this holy land aspires to live well, striving to fully satisfy their material, spiritual, and social needs. It is for this reason that individuals remain constantly active.

Activity is one of the basic conditions necessary for human existence.

Labor is the highest form of activity. From a philosophical point of view, the most adequate definition of the concept of "human" is "Humo agens", that is, "man in action". Of course, the form of activity and work is different, it includes practical, intellectual and spiritual processes in production, culture, public works, scientific works and other areas of life.

Carrying out activities in an irregular manner, without following the applicable laws, standards, and instructions, can not only cause injury or damage but, in some cases, can also lead to death. Naturally, this necessitates the organization of protection for individuals against all types of natural, technical, anthropogenic, ecological, and other dangerous factors in their activities on a scientific basis. The main goal and tasks of the science of 'Safety of Life Activities' are aimed at solving this problem, and this science is implemented based on its own laws, methods, and principles.

Labor protection consists of a set of activities and a system of tools aimed at eliminating various types of risks that occur in human production activities and learning ways to protect against them. Laws, statutes, standards, instructions, rules, and sanitary-technical norms are created based on scientific and theoretical research to ensure human labor safety. Additionally, creating a continuous education and training system for studying and developing these measures is important

MAIN PART. There are dangerous and harmful factors in the performance of work to improve the safety of employees, increase work efficiency. Employees must study, receive guidance, have their knowledge tested and undergo professional technical training in accordance with their professions and types of work..[3]

The main goal of labor protection is to provide theoretical knowledge on the dangerous factors that arise during the labor activity of workers and people in production, their causes, and ways of elimination. This aims at ensuring labor

safety and creating safe and healthy working conditions, as well as forming practical skills

Creating comfortable, safe and healthy working conditions for people requires solving the following tasks:

- Increased wind acceleration when working outdoors.
- Formation of electrical discharges in the atmosphere (lightning).
- Insufficient melting of the working zone.
- Excessive physical stress and mental fatigue.[4]

Appropriate changes should be made to the list in the case of changes in technological processes or the introduction of new production equipment that leads to the appearance of new harmful substances or the reduction of the level of exposure to dangerous and harmful factors.

Employee protective equipment involves shielding employees from the harmful and dangerous factors of the production environment. This protection is provided through the use of modern personal protective equipment, in accordance with the requirements of relevant standards for worker safety. Personal protective equipment is provided to workers and employees by the enterprise according to the established procedure. Workers using protective equipment should be informed about its use, protective properties, and validity period, and they should receive training on how to use them effectively

SAFETY REQUIREMENTS IN THE PERFORMANCE OF WORKS.

The organization of the workplace should ensure the firm standing of the worker, free movement, and visual control of their activities, as well as the safe execution of labor operations. Hazardous areas must be identified with safety signs and labels. Power lines and electrical distributors are de-energized in the vicinity of live or live parts of electrical equipment when there is a risk of accidental contact with them. In such cases, a sign should be hung on the extinguishing equipment saying: 'Do not turn on! Work is underway!' It is forbidden to use metal ladders

and ladders in situations where it is not possible to turn off the voltage during work. Crowding of people and overloading of materials in the air or on other equipment beyond their calculated load-carrying capacity is prohibited. Personal equipment should be stored in bags or special sorters.

CONCLUSION.Therefore, it can be concluded that it would be appropriate to approach employees based on their mental characteristics when providing a safe and healthy work environment. One of the most effective ways to implement a healthy work environment in industrial enterprises is through the proper distribution of work and full compliance with safety rules, ensuring there are no accidents in the work process and maintaining stable operations.

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